

Organizational Cynicism and Turnover Intention in Hotel Industry at Delhi

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The feeling of organizational cynicism is the negative aspects of the organizational behaviour arena and is major obstacles in the smooth functioning of the business firm. The current study focuses on hotel industry at Delhi, to gauge the association of organizational cynicism with turnover intention and to check statistically whether the association is significant or not. The adapted questionnaire was the medium to capture the information related to the study and respondents were employees working in the hotel industry at Delhi. 249 samples from the population were analysed through SPSS (version 20). Reliability and factor analysis was found suitable in preliminary analysis. Thereafter, Simple Linear Regression was applied to report the association between the variables of the current study. Researchers have reported a poor and positive association, which was statistically insignificant. It was the inference that organizational cynicism behaviour has no effect on turnover intention in the hotel industry at Delhi, although such feelings are prevailing among the employees. The findings of the study will make aware to the owners of a business firm to minimize such attitude which detracts the performance of employees and organization, while shortcomings will provide the direction to identify the gap for further research.

Keywords: Hotel Industry, Organizational Cynicism, Organizational Performance, Turnover Intention

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Introduction

Human resources are an imperative and valuable asset that thrives the organization to achieve competitive advantage and desired outcomes. In this elusive business environment, it has become quite difficult for employers to retain their talented workforce due to cynicism and attrition intention. Organizational cynicism has been reported as one of the predictors of turnover intention (Shahzad & Mehmood, 2012). A cynical employee feels that organization is not taking a proper interest in employee development and utilizing it for their own purpose (Eaton, 2000).

Researches on the hotel industry clearly postulate that the turnover rate of employees in the hotels of many countries is a serious issue that requires immediate propensity to suppress. In line with these facts, the current study has tried to investigate the degree of association between cynicism and turnover intention and the effect of the predictor variable (organizational cynicism) on the dependent variable (turnover intention) in the hotel industry at Delhi. The available literature associated with the variables of the current study comprehends that the feeling of cynicism is influencing the degree of intention to quit the organization. It was reported in previous researches that the organizations which have higher cynicism tend to have higher turnover intention as compared to the organizations which exhibit a lower degree of turnover intention (Khan, 2014, as cited in Lather, et al., 2011). Adams (1965) has demonstrated that when organizations do not payback according to the performance of employees, such a situation creates disillusion among the employees and leads to turnover intention and absenteeism.

The researches associated with organizational cynicism reveals that it develops negative feeling among the employees towards their organization. The consequences of organizational cynicism are detrimental for the organization and these are dissatisfaction, lack of job commitment, disengagement and finally

Employees make up their mind to switch the organization (Nair & Kamalanabhan, 2010). Attrition of the employees not only influences the productivity of the organization, but also generates numerous problems like recruitment and selection cost of new employees, which ultimately strains the productivity and profitability of the organization (Rehman, Karim, Rafiq, & Mansoor, 2012). Thus, on the basis of extant literature, it can be comprehended that feeling of cynicism and turnover intention exists in almost every sector across the globe. It is straining the root of the organization, especially the hotel industry which is suffering from the problems of organizational cynicism and attrition at large scale. Therefore, organizations should pay attention on such susceptible issues and take unmet action to harness these issues, which is one of the main obstacles in the development of the organization.

Review of Literature

The researchers have made an in-depth study of pertinent literature related to the current study and have fragmented it into three sections. The first section demonstrates the literature pertaining to organizational cynicism and the second one elucidates the extant work on turnover intention. The last portion highlights the literature pertaining to the association between both variables i.e. organizational cynicism and turnover intention.

Studies Related to Organizational Cynicism

The study conducted on workers employed in American company defined cynicism as a negative and distrustful feeling with authority and organization (Bateman, Sakano, & Fujita, 1992). Wanous, Reichers, and Austin (1994) have explained that organizational cynicism is the feeling of negativity, which arises due to change that the organization will incorporate in near future. The employee feels that the authority involved in the change process is lacking in terms of knowledge, skill and competency. Thereafter, Dean, Brandes, and Dharwadkar (1998) have identified three subdivisions of the term cynicism namely cognitive, affective and behavioural.

Tükeltürk, Aydın, Perçin, and Güzel, (2012) have made an attempt to know the factors that persuade organizational cynicism and they reported that high degree stress, improper social support, organizational complications, low job autonomy and management integrity are the influencing factors of organizational cynicism. Iqbal (2013) also posits that one of the precursors of organizational cynicism is job autonomy, which reduces the level of cynicism and enhances the motivation and engagement level of employees towards the job and organization.

Srivastava and Adams, (2011) in their study, in which employees from different organizations were taken into consideration, have reported that supervisor-subordinate relationship, job satisfaction, cooperation among the employee's declines due to cynicism, which develops negative consequences for an organization. Ozler and Ceren, (2011) are in compliance with previous researches that organizational cynicism has negative outcomes for the organization in various forms like disillusion, distrust and desperation with the organization.

Abraham (2000) and Goldner, Ritti, and Ference (1977) have elucidated that affective and behavioural outcomes are the most common consequences of organizational cynicism. These are low organizational commitment, lack of determination and less degree of job satisfaction.

Studies Related to Turnover Intention

The study conducted by Dreher (1982) regarding the association between high performers and their intention to quit the organization has reported that high performers are more satisfied with their job as they get reward and recognition according to performance. They have less intention to quit the organization. In their study Zimmerman and Darnold, (2009) have also tried to investigate the degree of association of employees performance with their intention to quit. They are also in consistent with the findings of Dreher (1982) that the performance of employees has a high degree of association with the intention to quit the organization.

In numerous studies, the researchers have correlated the training and development with turnover intention and had reported that those employees, who get proper training and development opportunity might have less intention to quit the organization (Shore, Tetrick, Lynch, & Barksdale, 2006). The study carried out by Mohamad and Azzat, (2006) in five-star hotels regarding the impact of training and development on turnover intention of the employees have reported a positive association between these two variables.

In their study, Karatepe, Yavas, and Babakus (2007) have highlighted that support from supervisor, training and development opportunities, reward and recognition and level of job satisfaction is influencing the degree of turnover intention and contributes a vital portion in diminishing the degree of intention to quit the job. Rehman, Karim, Rafiq, and Mansoor, (2012) have posited that decrease level of satisfaction and motivation are predictors of higher employee turnover (Mobley, Horner, & Hollings Worth, 1978).

Thus, it can be summarised that a sound work environment, support from the employer, the opportunity of career growth and adequate compensation systems are controlling factors of turnover intention in an organization. There is a need to develop a positive behaviour among the workforce towards their employers and so that employee should feel more satisfied, committed and engage towards the job and have less intention to quit the organization.

Studies Related to Organizational Cynicism and Turnover Intention

The study conducted by Khan (2014) so as to identify the association of organizational cynicism with turnover intention among the employees employed in banks of Pakistan has reported a positive and significant association between these two variables. He further asserted that intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction partially arbitrates the association of organizational cynicism with turnover intention and job satisfaction was found strong antecedent of turnover intention in the banking sector

Of Pakistan. Beheiri, Ahmed, and Aboul-Ela (2018) have reported that organizational cynicism plays a positive role in the turnover intention of the employees working in Nola cupcakes in Egypt.

In their study, Shahzad and Mehmood, (2012) have reported that feeling of cynicism may be a cause of employee turnover because such kind of situations creates the feeling of attrition among the employees. Nair and Kamalanabhan, (2010) are in compliance with the findings of previous researches and observed that organizational cynicism has negative consequences for the employee as well as for the organization in the form of frustration, dissatisfaction and lack of commitment towards the job and finally employee tends to quit the organization.

Ay and Unal, (2016) have made an attempt to investigate the effect of organizational cynicism on intention to quit the job among the staff working in state hospital in Tokat (Turkey) and result was inconsistent with the findings of earlier researchers. They reported that organizational cynicism had no effect on turnover intention in the hospital under study. They summarised that cynical attitude is not influencing the turnover intention of the employees. While, Volpe, Mohammed, Hopkins, Shapiro, and Dellasega (2014) in their study on U.S. healthcare providers regarding the influence of cynicism on organizational commitment, job satisfaction and intention to quit the hospital have observed a negative association of cynicism with organizational commitment and job satisfaction, while it was positively correlated with intention to leave the hospital.

Research Questions and Hypotheses Development

In the study, researchers have tried to investigate the association of organizational cynicism with turnover intention among the employees in the hotel industry in Delhi. The researchers formulated certain questions and have developed the hypotheses to find out the answer to the questions.

Question 1: Is there any association

That exists between organizational cynicism and turnover intention in the hotel Industry in Delhi?

Question 2: if so, is it statistically significant or not?

Ho1: Organizational cynicism and turnover intention have no significant association in the hotels under study.

Ha1: Organizational cynicism and turnover intention have a significant association in the hotels under study.

Research Methodology

The study includes primary and secondary sources of data for achieving the objectives of the current study. Primary sources have been used to empirically test the hypotheses and secondary sources cover the conceptual portion of the study.

Research Population, Method of Data Collection and Sample Size

The employees working in the hotel industry in Delhi are considered to be included in the research population for the current study. But due to time, financial and other constraints, it was not possible for the researchers to catch every individual to collect the information related to the current study. That is why selected samples were taken into consideration from the research population for the study.

The data was obtained through an adapted questionnaire, through convenient sampling. The questionnaire consists of two sections, the first section highlights the information associated to demographic variables of the employees and the second section covers the degree of organizational cynicism and turnover intention on a Likert's scale ranging from 1 to 5. In order to evaluate the accuracy and flow of the questionnaire, a small sample of 47 respondents was taken into consideration for pilot testing and feedback was received from respondents regarding the confirmation about the flow and accuracy of the questionnaire.

315 questionnaire were circulated among the respondents employed in various hotels

Located in Delhi. Researchers have received 267 filled questionnaire, some of the questionnaires were incomplete and finally, 249 questionnaires found perfect in all respect were analysed for hypotheses testing.

Reliability of the Data

Reliability of data is related to consistency in the findings, when the study is repeated (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). For the current study reliability was assessed through Cronbach’s alpha, which evaluates the consistency among the statements. The Cronbach’s alpha value is presented in table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Reliability of all Statements

Value of Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Statements
.809	10

Table 2: Variable Wise Reliability

Name of the Variable	Code	No. of Statements	Cronbach's Alpha Value
Organizational Cynicism	OC	5	.804
Turnover Intention	TI	5	.959

As per table 1, the overall reliability of statements is .809 and table 2 depicts the reliability of predictor and dependent variable, which are .804 and .959 respectively. The values of Cronbach’s alpha are above the suitable range as recommended by (George & Mallery, 2003; Nunnally, 1978). Reliability analysis indicates that data is suitable for analysis.

Factor Analysis

The researchers have checked the Sampling Adequacy and Sphericity test for the suitability of the data with the help of SPSS, which are shown in the table below.

Table 3: Results of KMO & Bartlett’s Test

KMO value	.830	
Bartlett’s test of Sphercity	Approx. Chi-Square	3305.206
	Df	45
	Sig	.000

The above Table 3 highlights that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value is .881, which lies in the range of great and is above the acceptable

Value i.e. 0.5 (Kaiser, 1974; Hutcheson & Sofroniou, 1999). Bartlett's Test was used to know the variation between the correlation matrix and identity matrix. The available literature suggested that the difference between these two is important for the suitability of data. In the current study significance value is .000, it can be interpreted that variation exists between correlation and identity matrix, which proves the appropriateness of the data for analysis.

Table 4: Output of Rotated Component Matrix(Insert Here)

Table 4 elucidates the value of the rotated component matrix. Principal Component Analysis was run to check the extraction of each statement, which is above the acceptable range i.e. above. 0.50.

Table 5: The output of Overall Variance Explained (insert Here)

The output of overall variance explained is presented in table 5, which highlights that there are three components, which have an Eigenvalue of more than one. These three components cover 90.034% of the whole variance. Thus, it can inference that all 10 statements may be assembled into three factors that covers a high portion (90.034) of the whole variance.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: Organizational cynicism and turnover intention have no significant association in the hotels under study. The researchers have applied Simple Linear Regression to empirically check the hypothesis.

Table 6: Correlation Result(Insert Here)

Table 6 represents the value of Pearson Correlation which is .088, it can be interpreted that there is a very low degree of association between organizational cynicism and turnover intention in the hotels under study. The value of correlations reveals that this association is positive and weak. Further, the researchers have applied Regression Analysis in order to know whether this association is significant or not.

Table 7: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.088a	.008	.004	.85540

Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Cynicism

Table 7 highlight the output of Regression Analysis, in which the R-value indicates the correlation between the expected and actual value of dependent value i.e. turnover intention. While R² value is .008, it means, less than one per cent variation in turnover intention is elucidated by organizational cynicism. Hence, it is clear indication that other factors are creating the feeling of turnover intention in the hotels under study.

Table 8: Simple Linear Regression: Coefficientsa (Insert Here)

In the above table 8, the unstandardized Beta value is .086, which inferences that one unit increase in the value of organizational cynicism, will lead to .086 unit increase in value of turnover intention. The table also elucidates that the impact of the predictor variable (organizational cynicism) on the dependent variable (turnover intention) is statistically insignificant as the significance value is .167, which is more than .05. It means, the null hypothesis is accepted and it can inference that organizational cynicism has an insignificant impact on turnover intention in the hotels under study.

Results and Discussions

The current study has made an attempt to investigate the association between organizational cynicism and turnover intention in the hotel industry in Delhi. The majority of extant literature deliberates that these two aspects are positively and significantly associated with each other. To identify this association, researchers have collected the information from the respondents working in the hotel industry in Delhi and empirically tested it by applying Regression Analysis.

It was reported that a positive association exist between the predictor variable (organizational cynicism) and turnover intention. This association

Is very low because the degree of Pearson correlation was 0.088. It was observed that less than one per cent variation in the degree of turnover intention was elucidated by organizational cynicism and if the level of organizational cynicism is enhance by one unit, there will an increment of .086 unit in the degree of turnover intention. The coefficient table asserted that organizational cynicism has an insignificant impact on turnover intention as the significance value is above .05. Therefore, from the findings of the current study, it can be contented that organizational cynicism is not inducing the level of turnover intention at a larger scale in the hotel industry in Delhi. It means, there might be other causes of the turnover intention of employees working in the hotel industry in Delhi.

The findings of this research are in consonance with the reporting of Ay and Unal, (2016) in which they reported that attitude of organizational cynicism has no effect on the intention to quit among the employees working in a state hospital in Tokat (Turkey). While in many types of research, organizational cynicism was highlighted as a strong predictor for creating the feeling of turnover intention and reported that organizational cynicism has a positive and statistically significant association with turnover intention in an organization (khan, 2014; Nair & Kamalanabhan, 2010; Shahzad & Mehmood, 2012; Volpe, Mohammed, Hopkins, Shapiro, & Dellasega, 2014; Beheiri, Ahmed, & Aboul-Ela, 2018).

Conclusion

The feeling of cynicism and turnover intention are negative aspect of the organizational behaviour arena and no organization is free from such negative attitudes. It is not only increasing the recruitment and selection cost but also strains the cordial working environment of the organization. This ultimately reduces the efficiency and profitability of the company. The current study is concerned with the hotel industry in Delhi, the level of organizational cynicism is more as compared to turnover intention and very poor association was reported. This association is statistically insignificant in the hotel industry in Delhi.

From the results of the current research, it may comprehend that cynicism is one of the causes of creating an intention to leave the organization, although it is not influencing the degree of turnover intention at a large scale. Nevertheless, there are other factors that are enabling turnover intention to grow among employees.

Therefore, it requires the immediate attention of policymakers and managers to suppress the problems of cynicism and should identify other factors, which generate the intention of attrition among the workers. The organization should exert remedial measures to control such issues, so as to ameliorate the efficiency and profitability of the company.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

Like every study, the current study has some limitations. Current study had included 249 sample only, future studies may enhance the number of the respondents so as to obtain more appropriate results. The findings of study are totally based on accuracy of information and cannot be generalise to Indian hotel industry. The study is restricted to hotel industry at Delhi, future researches can be carried out in different geographical areas of India. Current study is specific to hotel industry at Delhi, future researchers may opt the same study on other industries of Delhi. The researchers had identified the effect of organizational cynicism on turnover intention, future researchers may explore the effect of organizational cynicism on performance of the organization in terms of productivity and profitability.

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Table 4: Output of Rotated Component Matrix

No.		Initial	Extraction
1	OC1	1.000	.983
2	OC2	1.000	.983
3	OC3	1.000	.854
4	OC4	1.000	.856
5	OC5	1.000	.982
6	TI1	1.000	.898
7	TI2	1.000	.902
8	TI3	1.000	.722
9	TI4	1.000	.913
10	TI5	1.000	.911

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Table 5: Output of Overall Variance Explained

Components	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Variance in %	Cumulative Variance %
1	4.406	44.061	44.061
2	2.949	29.486	73.547
3	1.649	16.487	90.034

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Table 6: Correlation Result

		Turnover Intention	<i>Organizational Cynicism</i>
Pearson Correlation	Turnover Intention	1.000	.088
	<i>Organizational Cynicism</i>	.088	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Turnover Intention	.	.084
	<i>Organizational Cynicism</i>	.084	.
N	Turnover Intention	249	249
	<i>Organizational Cynicism</i>	249	249

Table 8: Simple Linear Regression: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sign.
		β	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.093	.190		11.014	.000
	<i>Organizational Cynicism</i>	.086	.062	.088	1.385	.167

a. Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention